

EARTH SCIENCES

MONITORING SPATIAL CHANGES IN WATER RESOURCES WITH GIS

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Abstract

With the help of satellite images, it is possible to more accurately monitor the area changes occurring in water basins. These images are considered one of the most modern and effective methods in this direction. With this method, it is possible to monitor the changes in water areas and develop preventive measures. Through satellite imagery, we can conduct comparative analysis by looking at the dynamics of changes in all water bodies - reservoirs, rivers, lakes, canals, glaciers and snow cover, wetlands, and groundwater.

Keywords: GIS, Mountain lakes, water resources, field change

How is analysis performed with GIS technologies?

1. Optical satellites (Landsat, Sentinel-2) are of great importance in obtaining satellite data of lakes and rivers
2. Even in cloudy weather conditions, observation of water resources can be carried out using Radar satellites (Sentinel-1).
3. GRACE and GRACE-FO satellites can determine changes in groundwater resources.
4. Materials obtained with GIS technologies are mainly analyzed and transferred to QGIS and ArcGIS programs and depicted on the map.

areas of water basins have been alarmingly affected by all the consequences of climate change.

An increase in the average temperature of water resources is observed. Of course, this situation leads to changes in the area of water resources. Lakes, which are an important component of land units, constitute up to 1% of the water resources of the hydrosphere. Despite having a very small percentage, these freshwater resources play an important role in the sustainable existence of the living environment in the ecosystem. Baku hosted an important event such as COP29 to solve such negative effects caused by climate change and examined ways to solve it. The emergence of sharp differences in water masses brings steps to be taken in this direction to the fore. The continuous increase in negative impacts leads to the activity and dynamism of this process. Remote Sensing has played a key role in investigating, studying and finding solutions to such global problems. This method obtains comprehensive information about the area without forcing observation on the ground, without physically observing the area. Remote sensing is used in a number of fields (military, humanitarian, geographical research). During its use, areas are studied using signals transmitted from the ground and aerosensor technologies are used. It is possible to collect visual information from the most dangerous and difficult-to-pass places through remote sensing.

Using satellite data, the detection and study of spatial changes in existing inaccessible water resources has become a key factor. Various artificial intelligence technologies are also of particular importance. The main topic of this article is to investigate the factors that cause spatial changes in the inaccessible mountainous lakes of Azerbaijan, to visually observe how they

What processes are monitored?	
I.	The effects of climate change on the spatial distribution of water resources are determined
II.	The impact on the reduction of water in reservoirs is assessed.
III.	Irrigation needs in agricultural areas are investigated and solutions are planned.
IV.	By identifying water scarcity problems, flood risks can be predicted in advance.

As we know, general water resources are very important for the entire ecosystem components in the world. Despite their great vital importance for all nature and living things, water resources are subject to very large anthropogenic impacts, and various reasons such as drought caused by global warming are creating major problems. Since the beginning of the 21st century, negative factors such as the annual rate of precipitation in all parts of the world's water resources (oceans, seas, lakes, rivers, glaciers, etc.) and the sharp change in the

change over the months. These lakes, along with their enchanting beauty and picturesque appearance, are striking in their inaccessibility, which has led to the under-research of these water resources. The territory of the Kalbajar-Lachin economic geographical region (in Kalbajar and Lachin), the territory of the Karabakh economic geographical region (Aghdara region) was taken as the object of research. Considering that these territories were under enemy occupation for a long time, the lack of attention to these territories is also evident in the lack of modern research work. The fact that foreigners were content with living, exploiting, and plundering in these territories once again proves their carelessness towards these territories, their lack of being original and eternal inhabitants.

In addition, research was conducted on 30 mountain lakes covering an area of 2 ha in the territories of Kalbajar, Lachin and Agdere. The total area of mountain lakes in that area is 900 ha. The largest lakes, covering 72% of the area, are Boyuk Alagol (Kalbajar), Ishikli Karagol (Lachin), Kichik Alagol (Kalbajar). Boyuk Alagol is located in the territory of the Karabakh volcanic plateau, in the Kalbajar region - 40°00' N. E. 45°44' N. W. geographical coordinates. The height of the lake is 2729 m above sea level. The maximum length is 3.7 km, and the widest is more than 9 m. Its volume is 24.3 million m³. The area of the lake is 5.1 km², and its length is 3670 m. The widest part is 2875 m, the average width is 1365 m, and the maximum depth is 9.4 m. There are also about 30 small lakes in this area, the largest of which is Kichik Alagöl after Boyuk Alagöl. Most of them dry up in the summer. The largest river is the Gurbagalı River, and 7 rivers flow into the lake. Kichik Alagöl is located at the geographical coordinates of 39°59'11" N. E. 45°44'01" N. W. The area of the lake is 0.9 km², and its length is 2000 m. The widest part is 825 m, and the length of the coastline is 5260 m. The deepest place is 4 m. Let's compare the difference in change for the first 4 months of 2020 and 2024. The area of the lake decreased by 63.2 ha between January 2020 (465.4 ha) and January 2024 (402.2 ha). A decrease of 41.4 ha was observed in February, 31.9 ha in March, and 84.8 ha in April. Let's look at the illustration below.

Based on the above description, we can say that the satellite image taken in 2020 and 2024 is the most important dynamic change image obtained within the scope of the study and forms the main part of the study. The satellite image from May 2021 shows the upper limit of the lake (497.5 ha), that is, the image with the largest area. The smallest area change was recorded in April 2024 (350.8 ha).

Let's look at the differences in the dynamics of change by looking at satellite images of Lake Kichik Alagol over the years.

Let's look at what analyses can be performed with satellite images:

Hydrology and changes, Environment and landscape, Time series comparison, High-level satellite images. For all water bodies, the change in surface area,

thickness and change of glacier cover over the years can be monitored by satellite and the images can be analyzed. During these observations, the volume of water, dynamic changes in the flow of the river can be monitored and evaluated with GIS analysis. The status of the lakeside areas (settlement, vegetation, wetland formations) can be assessed from satellite. Sentinel-2 (optical) and Sentinel-1 (radar) satellites allow the detection of shadow textural changes.

Work progress

First, the research area is determined. Satellite data is obtained. The obtained data about water bodies is transmitted. Statistical classification of the data is carried out according to time. Finally, all the obtained data is analyzed and the results are transferred to maps. It is this specificity in the research that helps to obtain more accurate information. For this reason, the demand for the use of GIS has been increasing in recent years. At this time, it is possible to demonstrate the effectiveness of digital technologies by analyzing changes in water surfaces over a certain period of time based on satellite images.

Water bodies can be analyzed using NDWI (Normalised Difference Water Index). The following formula is used.

$$NDWI = \frac{\text{Green} + \text{NIR}}{\text{Green} - \text{NIR}}$$

A long-term analysis is performed. Comparisons are made over the years. Water and land are separated and classified. Finally, the changes that have occurred are shown in percentage.

These results may be related to global climate change, increasing droughts, and expanding cropland. GIS and remote sensing methods allow for faster and larger-scale analyses than field observations. However, there are technical limitations such as cloudiness, atmospheric effects, and the timeliness of satellite images.

GIS technologies are an effective tool for long-term monitoring of water resources.

For government agencies and researchers, these methods can be a key tool in developing early warning systems and sound water management strategies.

Integration with higher resolution satellite imagery and weather models is proposed for future research.

According to these analyses, the water bodies with the most spatial changes observed in Azerbaijan are as follows:

Water Basin Main changes and causes

Coasts of the Caspian Sea	Narrowing/widening of the coastline; erosion; water level changes
Kura and Araz rivers	Decrease in flow, anthropogenic infrastructure, water losses
Mountain lakes (Boyuk Alagöl)	Area changes as a result of climate change and melting pressure
Lake Aggol	Archaicization of the water regime, use of anthropogenic water masses

References:

1. Azərbaycan Respublikasının Dövlət Statistika Komitəsi. (2023). Su ehtiyatları və su təchizatı üzrə statistik göstəricilər.
2. Climate Report: Qlobal iqlim dəyişikliklərinin Azərbaycan Respublikasına təsirlərinin kosmik monitorinqi
3. Climate Report: <https://climatereport.az/section/hydrosphere>
4. Climate Report: climatereport.az/section/monitoring-mountain-lakes
5. Hüseynova, S., & Hacıyeva, N. (2020). Azərbaycanın su ehtiyatlarının keyfiyyət vəziyyətinin GIS əsaslı monitorinqi. "Ekologiya və Hidrometeorologiya" jurnal,
6. World Bank. (2022). Water Security and Climate Resilience in Azerbaijan
7. United Nations Economic Commission for Europe (UNECE). (2011). Second Environmental Performance Review of Azerbaijan.
8. Azərbaycan Respublikasının Ekologiya və Təbii Sərvətlər Nazirliyi. (2020). Azərbaycanın su ehtiyatları və onların istifadəsi üzrə illik hesabat.
9. Abbasov, F. (2018). Azərbaycanın su ehtiyatlarının coğrafi tədqiqi və idarə olunması problemləri. Bakı: Bakı Universiteti Nəşriyyatı.
10. Məmmədov, R., & Qurbanova, L. (2019). Azərbaycan Respublikasında su ehtiyatlarının idarə olunması: İqlim dəyişmələri kontekstində yanaşmalar. Azərbaycan Milli Elmlər Akademiyası, Coğrafiya İnstitutu Elmi Əsərləri
11. Climate Report: climatereport.az/section/general-knowledge
12. Climate Report: climatereport.az/section/monitoring-caspian-sea
13. Climate Report: climatereport.az/section/monitoring-water-level-caspian-sea
14. Climate Report: climatereport.az/section/monitoring-water-level-kura-river